

PREVALENCE OF VITAMIN B12 DEFICIENCY AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Background: Vitamin B12 deficiency is an underrecognized complication among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), particularly in those on long-term metformin therapy. Peripheral neuropathy is one of the most disabling complications of diabetes, and its coexistence with vitamin B12 deficiency may worsen neurological outcomes.

Objectives: To determine the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency and to assess its association with peripheral neuropathy in patients with T2DM.

Study design & Setting: A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore over six months from January to June 2025.

Methodology: A total of 120 patients with T2DM were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. Serum vitamin B12 levels were measured and categorized as normal (>300 µg/mL), borderline (200–300 µg/mL), or deficient (<200 µg/mL). Peripheral neuropathy was assessed clinically using standard neurological examination. Demographic and clinical data, including age, gender, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels, were collected. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Chi-square test was applied to assess associations, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean age of participants was 49.7 ± 12.1 years, with 55.8% males. Vitamin B12 deficiency was observed in 21.7% and borderline levels in 18.3% of patients. Peripheral neuropathy was detected in 32.5% of patients. A statistically significant association was found between low vitamin B12 levels (deficient + borderline) and peripheral neuropathy ($p = 0.004$), while no significant associations were observed with age, gender, duration of diabetes, or HbA1c levels.

Conclusion: Vitamin B12 deficiency is common in T2DM patients and is significantly associated with peripheral neuropathy. Routine screening and timely correction of vitamin B12 deficiency may reduce diabetes-related neurological

complications.

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a major global health concern, affecting more than 537 million people worldwide, with projections suggesting a rise to 643 million by 2030. It is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia due to insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency, leading to a range of long-term complications.^{1,2} Among these complications, diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) is one of the most prevalent and debilitating, manifesting as pain, numbness, tingling, or burning sensations in the extremities. It not only reduces quality of life but also predisposes patients to foot ulcers, infections, and amputations, making its early recognition and prevention critically important.^{3,4}

Vitamin B12 (cobalamin) is an essential water-soluble vitamin required for DNA synthesis, erythropoiesis, and the maintenance of neurological function through myelin formation. Deficiency of vitamin B12 is a well-established cause of peripheral neuropathy, characterized by axonal degeneration and demyelination, leading to sensory and motor impairments.⁵ In patients with T2DM, the risk of vitamin B12 deficiency is increased, primarily due to prolonged use of metformin, which remains the first-line oral hypoglycemic drug.⁶ Metformin impairs vitamin B12 absorption in the terminal ileum through alterations in calcium-dependent membrane action, and this effect intensifies with higher doses and longer treatment duration. Other factors such as age, dietary insufficiency, gastrointestinal disorders, and chronic illnesses may also contribute.⁷

The clinical overlap between diabetic neuropathy and B12 deficiency-induced neuropathy complicates the accurate diagnosis of neuropathic symptoms in diabetic patients. While diabetic neuropathy is attributed to chronic hyperglycemia-induced microvascular damage, oxidative stress, and advanced glycation end-products, vitamin B12 deficiency leads to defective myelination and neuronal injury.⁸ Both pathways may act synergistically, aggravating the

severity of neuropathic manifestations in T2DM patients. Importantly, unlike diabetic neuropathy, neuropathy due to vitamin B12 deficiency is potentially reversible if identified early and treated with supplementation, highlighting the clinical significance of evaluating vitamin B12 status in this population.⁹

Several studies across different populations have reported variable prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency among T2DM patients, ranging from 6% to over 30%, with a significant proportion exhibiting neuropathic symptoms. However, regional differences in dietary habits, healthcare practices, and genetic factors influence these variations.¹⁰ In South Asian countries, where vegetarian diets are common and awareness regarding vitamin supplementation is limited, the prevalence may be considerably higher. Despite the clinical relevance, B12 screening is not routinely performed in many healthcare settings for T2DM patients, leading to underdiagnosis and delayed management.^{11,12}

Given the rising burden of diabetes and the significant morbidity associated with neuropathy, exploring the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency and its relationship with peripheral neuropathy in T2DM patients is essential. Such evidence will not only provide insights into potentially modifiable risk factors but also guide preventive and therapeutic strategies to improve patient outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore from Jan to June 2025. A total of 120 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were enrolled. The sample size of 120 was calculated using the formula for single population proportion, keeping a prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency in diabetics at 30%, a confidence interval of 95%, and a margin of error of 8%. Patients aged 30–70 years with a confirmed diagnosis of type 2 diabetes mellitus for at least one year were included. Exclusion criteria were

patients with type 1 diabetes, chronic renal failure, liver disease, pernicious anemia, prior vitamin B12 supplementation, or other known causes of neuropathy such as alcoholism, hypothyroidism, and connective tissue disorders. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to inclusion in the study.

Demographic and clinical data including age, gender, duration of diabetes, comorbidities, and drug history with particular emphasis on metformin use were recorded on a predesigned proforma. Peripheral neuropathy was assessed using a detailed clinical neurological examination along with the Michigan Neuropathy Screening Instrument (MNSI), which comprised both a symptom questionnaire and a structured physical examination. Patients with a score ≥ 2.5 on the physical examination component of the MNSI were labeled as having peripheral neuropathy. Venous blood samples were obtained after overnight fasting for the measurement of serum vitamin B12 levels, fasting blood sugar, HbA1c, and other relevant biochemical parameters. Vitamin B12 levels were measured using chemiluminescent immunoassay. Patients with serum vitamin B12 levels < 200 pg/mL were classified as deficient, those between $200-300$ pg/mL were considered borderline, and levels > 300 pg/mL were taken as normal.

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Quantitative variables such as age, duration of diabetes, HbA1c, and serum vitamin B12 levels were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, whereas qualitative variables such as gender, presence of neuropathy, and categories of vitamin B12 status were presented as frequencies and percentages. The association between vitamin B12 deficiency and peripheral neuropathy was assessed using chi-square test, while independent sample t-test and ANOVA were applied for comparison of means where appropriate. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study included 120 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, with a mean age of 49.7 ± 12.1 years. Slightly more than half of the participants (55.8%) were aged 50 years or younger, while 50.0% were older than 50 years. There was a male predominance, with 67 (55.8%) males compared to 53 (44.2%) females. The mean duration of diabetes was 9.8 ± 5.9 years, with 62 (51.7%) patients having diabetes for ≤ 10 years and 58 (48.3%) for more than 10 years. Glycemic control assessment showed a mean HbA1c of $8.0 \pm 1.7\%$, with 56 (46.7%) patients having HbA1c $\leq 8\%$ and 64 (53.3%) with HbA1c greater than 8%, as given in Table 1.

The distribution of vitamin B12 status revealed that the majority of patients, 72 (60.0%), had normal levels. Vitamin B12 deficiency was identified in 26 (21.7%) patients, while 22 (18.3%) were in the borderline range, as presented in Table 2. Peripheral neuropathy was found in 39 (32.5%) patients, while 81 (67.5%) patients showed no clinical evidence of neuropathy. This indicates that almost one-third of the studied population suffered from peripheral neuropathy, as shown in Table 3.

Stratification of peripheral neuropathy with respect to various demographic and clinical parameters demonstrated no statistically significant difference when analyzed by gender ($p = 0.498$), age group ($p = 0.247$), duration of diabetes ($p = 0.901$), or HbA1c levels ($p = 0.857$). However, vitamin B12 status showed a significant association, with neuropathy present in 47.9% of patients having deficient or borderline vitamin B12 levels compared to only 22.2% in those with normal levels ($p = 0.004$). These finding highlights vitamin B12 deficiency as an important contributor to neuropathic manifestations among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, as given in Table 4.

Table 1. Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients (n = 120)

Variable	Categories	n (%)
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	49.7 ± 12.1

	≤50 years	67 (55.8%)
	>50 years	60 (50.0%)
Gender	Male	67 (55.8%)
	Female	53 (44.2%)
Duration of Diabetes	Mean ± SD	9.8 ± 5.9 years
	≤10 years	62 (51.7%)
	>10 years	58 (48.3%)
HbA1c (%)	Mean ± SD	8.0 ± 1.7
	≤8%	56 (46.7%)
	>8%	64 (53.3%)

Table 2. Distribution of Vitamin B12 Status (n = 120)

Vitamin B12 Status	n (%)
Normal	72 (60.0%)
Deficient	26 (21.7%)
Borderline	22 (18.3%)

Table 3. Frequency of Peripheral Neuropathy (n = 120)

Peripheral Neuropathy	n (%)
Yes	39 (32.5%)
No	81 (67.5%)

Table 4. Stratification of Peripheral Neuropathy with Respect to Different Variables (n = 120)

Variable	Categories	No n (%)	Yes n (%)	p-value
Gender	Male	43 (64.2%)	24 (35.8%)	0.498
	Female	38 (71.7%)	15 (28.3%)	
Age	≤50 years	42 (70.0%)	18 (30.0%)	0.247
	>50 years	39 (65.0%)	21 (35.0%)	
Duration of DM	≤10 years	42 (67.7%)	20 (32.3%)	0.901
	>10 years	39 (67.2%)	19 (32.8%)	
HbA1c	≤8%	37 (66.1%)	19 (33.9%)	0.857
	>8%	44 (68.8%)	20 (31.2%)	
Vitamin B12 Status	Normal	56 (77.8%)	16 (22.2%)	0.004*
	Deficient + Borderline	25 (52.1%)	23 (47.9%)	

DISCUSSION

Vitamin B12 plays an essential role in neurological function, DNA synthesis, and red blood cell formation. Deficiency of this micronutrient is increasingly recognized in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), partly due to dietary insufficiency and the long-

term use of metformin.¹³ Peripheral neuropathy, one of the most debilitating complications of diabetes, may share an association with vitamin B12 deficiency, worsening patient morbidity. Early detection of B12 deficiency in diabetics is critical to prevent irreversible nerve damage.¹⁴ The burden of both diabetes and its

complications is rising rapidly in developing countries, making this association a significant public health concern. Understanding the prevalence and correlation will help optimize management strategies for affected patients.

In the present study, vitamin B12 deficiency was observed in 21.7% of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), while 18.3% had borderline levels, giving an overall prevalence of suboptimal vitamin B12 status in 40.0% of participants. Peripheral neuropathy was documented in 32.5% of patients and showed a significant association with vitamin B12 deficiency and borderline levels ($p = 0.004$). These findings are consistent with global and regional data, though the magnitude varies across studies due to differences in population characteristics, sample size, metformin exposure, and diagnostic thresholds.

Miyan et al. (2020) reported a prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency of 3.9% among metformin users and 2.1% among non-users, while insufficiency was 18.4% and 27.9% respectively. Although their deficiency rate was lower than ours (21.7%), their large multicenter cohort ($n = 932$) highlighted the relationship between metformin use, hyperhomocysteinemia, and higher vibration perception threshold (VPT > 25) as well as DN4 ≥ 4 , indicating clinically significant neuropathy.¹⁵ Similarly, Nadeem et al. (2025) found subnormal vitamin B12 levels (≤ 300 pg/mL) in 28% of 150 T2DM patients, of whom 6.7% were frankly deficient and 21.3% inadequate, while diabetic neuropathy was diagnosed in 21.3%.¹⁶ Importantly, 68.7% of neuropathy patients had subnormal vitamin B12, underscoring the inverse association between B12 levels and neuropathy severity (coefficient = -115.6, 95% CI -164.1 to -67.0), which closely aligns with our significant correlation.¹⁶

In contrast, Hayat et al. (2025) reported a much higher prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency (48.2%), especially in patients older than 45 years (54.7% vs. 13.6% in younger, $p < 0.001$) and those with diabetes duration > 5 years (72.8% vs. 13.8%, $p < 0.001$). Although our study did not find significant stratification by age or duration, their findings highlight the cumulative effect of

diabetes chronicity.¹⁷ Khalaf et al. (2019) reported deficiency in 29% of 66 T2DM patients, similar to our observed prevalence, but did not find correlations with metformin dose ($p = 0.16$) or duration ($p = 0.09$).¹⁸ This contrasts with Rehman et al. (2025), who found that deficiency rates increased from 20% in those on metformin < 5 years to 65% in those > 10 years, with neuropathy present in 53.3%.¹⁹

Dias et al. (2023) further emphasized that low vitamin B12 was linked to neurological symptoms and suggested supplementation with methylcobalamin, which improved neuropathic manifestations.²⁰ Similarly, Khyalappa et al. (2020) documented deficiency in 29% and intermediate levels in 33%, with significant associations between peripheral neuropathy, vitamin B12 deficiency ($p < 0.05$), and duration of metformin use ($p < 0.01$).²¹

Taken together, our findings support the growing evidence that vitamin B12 deficiency is common in T2DM and significantly associated with peripheral neuropathy. While the prevalence in our cohort (21.7% deficient, 40% suboptimal) was somewhat lower than reported in Hayat et al. (48.2%) and Rehman et al. (65% with long-term metformin use),¹⁹ it is consistent with Nadeem et al. (28%)¹⁷ and Khalaf et al. (29%). The consistent association across multiple studies strengthens the argument for routine screening of vitamin B12 in T2DM, particularly for patients with neuropathy or prolonged metformin therapy.¹⁸

This study highlights the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency in T2DM patients, a relatively underexplored area in our local population. The use of biochemical testing for vitamin B12 and objective criteria for peripheral neuropathy strengthens the validity of findings. Stratification across demographic and clinical variables adds depth to the analysis. However, the single-center nature of the study limits generalizability to wider populations. The cross-sectional design prevents establishment of causality between vitamin B12 deficiency and neuropathy. A relatively modest sample size may also limit the detection of weaker associations.

CONCLUSION

Vitamin B12 deficiency was found to be prevalent among patients with type 2 diabetes and showed a significant association with peripheral neuropathy. These findings underscore the importance of routine screening and timely supplementation. Larger multicenter prospective studies are warranted to confirm and expand upon these observations.

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